

Tafattuq al-aḥkām

also known as “تفتُّق الأَكمام”, “Épanouissement de la fleur ou étude sur la femme dans l’islam”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Islamic Traditions, Sunni, Text, Islamic modernization, Islamic Theology

Šayz (شيخ) Muḥammad al-Sanūsī (محمد السنوسي) wrote and published the text at hand in 1890. The book was somewhat famous because, despite having been written by a scholar educated in conservative al-Zaytuna mosque, it was one of the first in Tunisia to rally for women's education. The book covers almost all of the Qur'anic dispositions regarding women, such as polygyny and testimony, from a conservative point of view that aligns with hegemonic interpretations of the times. The only topic that is portrayed under a different light is that of education. The book is filled with Qur'anic quotations as well as ahadith (أحاديث) to back the author's explanations of said issues and the laws related to them. Despite the fact that the book was not too well-known (except among fellow Zaytuna scholars), it did serve as a precedent for the educational reform, particularly with regards to the inclusion of women in education. The time scope we have chosen for the present entry reflects the period from the publication of the book until the Tunisian independence because it was in 1956 that the Law of Personal Status was published. Considering the topics covered by the text at hand and those present in the aforementioned law, we believe it is safe to assume that what little influence the text at hand could possibly have had in Tunisian society and the female emancipation and educational reform debates ended after the proclamation of the law.

Date Range: 1890 CE - 1956 CE

Region: Tunisia

Region tags: Africa, Northern Africa, Tunisia

Tunisia

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Mohammed Essnoussi, *Épanouissement de la fleur ou étude sur la femme dans l’islam*, translated by Mohammed Mohieddin Essnoussi and Abd el Kadr Kebaili, Tunis, Imprimerie Rapide, 1987.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k6204389q/f20.image.textelimage>
- Source 1 Description: French translation of the book.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– I don't know

Notes: The author was a Zaytuna scholar and had worked there before turning to journalism and the notarial profession. He had worked as a counselor for various ministers too. As such, he was not paid to write this book nor was he officially funded by the polity, but the salary he had made in all of these professions as well as his work as a journalist were what allowed him to write the book at hand and some of that salary did come from official, government-related posts.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: Despite the fact that at this point in time classical Arabic was still widely used in writing, the author did an effort to update the language as much as possible so that, while the text kept a very formal and scholarly air, it was trying to be accessible for people with a lower cultural and educational background.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Notes: It appears that the intended readership was made up of fellow Zaytuna scholars or judges, that is, mostly people with a religious background. However, members of the modernist elite who had no particular ties to either Zaytuna or the religious milieu did read the book.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned in the introduction, the text at hand is not too reformist or modernist in its content because it mostly sides with hegemonic interpretations of the Qur'an. However, it made an effort to strive for educational reform and, as such, made a reformist statement that women should be included in said reform and that they should be allowed to study just like any man was. As a result, the text can very well be considered part of the reformist movements, but in its beginnings.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– No

Notes: There are different editions, all of which contain the same text, as well as translations to French.

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: None

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: Although the text talks about many legal dispositions derived from the Qur'an, the text itself is

not a legal code nor does it intend to change the one in use at the time of its publication. In fact, the only 'change' between what was common practice at the time and what the text called for had to do with education, not the law. As such, it had little to no impact in the legal code or its interpretations.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: However, it is not particularly stressed by the text at hand.

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– I don't know

Notes: Regardless of what was usual in other Islamic writings of the time, this issue does not appear in the text at hand.

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: However, the text at hand does not elaborate on this. It merely mentions that both men and women would be equally rewarded or punished for their deeds in the afterlife.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– I don't know

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– I don't know

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– I don't know

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes

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↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: God is all-knowing.

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward

– Yes

↳ Can punish

– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: The Qur'an was God's message to humanity.

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Notes: The text makes no mention of either angels or junun (جنون).

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– Yes

↳ Adultery

– Yes

↳ Incest

– Yes

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– No

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– I don't know

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

↳ Other sexual practices

– Yes

Notes: Only heterosexual practices are allowed.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– I don't know

Notes: Technically yes, but it is not expressed in the text at hand.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– I don't know

Notes: Same as with disrespecting elders, it is supposed to be so (when conducting and/or participating in rituals), but the text at hand does not talk about personal hygiene.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– I don't know

Notes: Vid. previous note.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– Yes

Notes: But not in the present text.

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– I don't know

Notes: In most of the Islamic scholarly tradition yes, but it is not stated in the text at hand.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– Yes

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– No

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– No

↳ Other?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– I don't know

Notes: It would appear so, but the text does not go into details or mention it openly.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Notes: The text revolves around Islamic laws and regularly states that these are immutable because they were directly dictated by God. What is changeable is how human beings interpret them (and, as a result, how they are enforced). As such, the laws and norms themselves are believed to be unchangeable but certain interpretations of said laws could be contested. This only happens in the text with regards to the education of women: something that the author argues as being God's law, but that had been wrongly interpreted in the past, according to al-Sanūsī.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– No

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

Notes: Particularly with regards to veiling.

Reference: Essnoussi, Mohammed. *Épanouissement De La Fleur Ou Étude Sur La Femme Dans L'islam*. Edited by Mohammed Essnoussi Mohieddin and Abd el Kadr Kebaïli. Tunis: Imprimerie Rapide, n.d.. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k6204389q/f20.image.textelimage>. p.23-25

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

Reference: Essnoussi, Mohammed. *Épanouissement De La Fleur Ou Étude Sur La Femme Dans L'islam*. Edited by Mohammed Essnoussi Mohieddin and Abd el Kadr Kebaïli. Tunis: Imprimerie Rapide, n.d.. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k6204389q/f20.image.textelimage>. p.19

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

Notes: Only heterosexuality is permitted.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Notes: Only heterosexuality is permitted.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: Although it is a requirement in Islam, it is not mentioned in this text.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Notes: Vid. previous note.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Notes: Although the author received some backlash due to his view on women's education, it was not so big that we could say that he faced marginalization of some sort.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Notes: Again, despite being mandatory for Islam, it is not mentioned in the text.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Notes: Vid. previous note.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A nation-state

Notes: Despite the fact that Tunisia was, by the time the book was published, under French rule, the author sided with the nationalists and, taking into consideration the national liberation which took place in 1956, I believe we can talk in terms of a nation-state.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– I don't know

Notes: The text does not specify an institutionalized care per se, but often states that it is a woman's duty to care for the children in her household. The elderly and infirm are not mentioned specifically, but it is safe to assume that the author viewed this in the same manner in which he viewed childrearing (ie. expected women to take care of it).

Reference: Essnoussi, Mohammed. *Épanouissement De La Fleur Ou Étude Sur La Femme Dans L'islam*. Edited by Mohammed Essnoussi Mohieddin and Abd el Kadr Kebaili. Tunis: Imprimerie Rapide, n.d.. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k6204389q/f20.image.texteImage>. p.34-35

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Notes: Surprisingly enough, the text does not tackle widows or divorcees in detail. The latter are mentioned in passing and the former are not even mentioned but when referring to a specific woman who was a widow. Therefore, compensations are nor described nor discussed.

Reference: Essnoussi, Mohammed. *Épanouissement De La Fleur Ou Étude Sur La Femme Dans L'islam*. Edited by Mohammed Essnoussi Mohieddin and Abd el Kadr Kebaili. Tunis: Imprimerie Rapide, n.d.. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k6204389q/f20.image.texteImage>. p.9, p.21, p.19, p.35

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text does not enter into too many details as to what educational institutions should be like, but it does insist on the need to build schools and for said schools to be available for all Muslims, regardless of their gender.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– I don't know

Notes: The author viewed natural sciences as being derived from God's knowledge and, as such, they had a place under the idea of the so called "Islamic sciences". Therefore, it is unclear whether the author supported non-religious education (highly unlikely) or thought that religious education had to be updated to include sciences and other secular subjects too (highly likely).

Reference: Essnoussi, Mohammed. *Épanouissement De La Fleur Ou Étude Sur La Femme Dans L'islam*. Edited by Mohammed Essnoussi Mohieddin and Abd el Kadr Kebaili. Tunis: Imprimerie Rapide, n.d.. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k6204389q/f20.image.textelImage>. p.36

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: However, the text does not specify whether women and men should be taught the same curriculum.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: According to larger textual tradition, yes, as women were often barred from receiving an education. According to the text at hand, no.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: Mainly linked to social development and regarding the country as a more modern and productive one.

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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